

NEWSERA - Citizen Science as the
new paradigm for Science
Communication

Deliverable 7.1

Data Management Plan

Revision: v2.0

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- CO:** Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
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STATEMENT OF ORIGINALITY

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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SUMMARY

This document contains the NEWSERA Project Data Management Plan (DMP). The tools and strategies used for providing open access to research data are also presented.

The **main objective of the DMP** was to ensure from the very beginning that **all generated data were Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR)**. An analysis of the main elements of the data management policy that the consortium used was provided by July 2020.

The structure of this document responds to the **Open Research Data Pilot of the European Commission**, which seeks to enable open access and reuse of research data generated by Horizon 2020 projects. There are **two main pillars** to the Pilot: **developing a DMP** and **providing open access** to research data, if possible.

The overall objective of NEWSERA was to show the possibilities of **citizen science as an inclusive, broad and powerful channel of scientific communication**. Citizen science allows for increased trust in scientific communication and, in turn, in science in general. While opening up science and innovation to the whole society, citizen science improves scientific training and promotes critical thinking, reducing the possibilities of false news. NEWSERA has analysed and evaluated the complex and multidirectional science communication strategies, including digital and non-digital ones, addressed to **quadruple helix stakeholders** - that is, **communities** including the third sector, **the State** and public sector, **the market** and private sector, and **academia** - in citizen science projects across Europe, as the new paradigm for science communication.

As it is stated in the JRC document [Survey report on data management in Citizen Science Projects](#) (Schade et al., 2016), we paid attention not only to the legal aspects regarding different countries and cities, but also to the socio-cultural characteristics. This is a minimum requirement for achieving our objective of **developing a co-created process**, based on **a bottom-up approach** as much as possible.

This deliverable was presented as a **living document**, updated when needed, according to the **cross-cutting nature of the ethical aspects**, during the development of the whole project and especially in view of the **emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic**.

Some modifications have been introduced in this final version, related to the next aspects:

- It is noted that Science for Change, the lead partner, will take over the management of the data that were generated during the development of NEWSERA, replacing IBERCIVIS since the end of NEWSERA.
- Explanation is provided on the modifications of the informed consent forms - including explicitly the name of the Data Protection Officer - and the clarification on "vulnerable persons" - children, young minors, and vulnerable adults -, modifications that were requested by the Commission after the review of the first period of the project.
- It is explained that a public acknowledgement of NEWSERA pilots and their representatives was introduced on the website, according to their informed consent.
- It is clarified that the changes to the Twitter policy in March 2023 did not affect the use of the Kampal tool as they occurred around the same time as the end of NEWSERA.
- Five new references have been added: four of them associated with three NEWSERA documents and another one to the Kampal tool.

With regard to the health crisis, now that three years have passed since the start of the pandemic, fortunately there have been no further issues, in terms of data management, beyond the adaptation of the informed consent format for online meetings.

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1. Acronyms

Acronym	Description
CitSciComm	Citizen Science Communication
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EAB	External Advisory Board
FB	formicablu
FC.ID	FCIENCIAS.ID Associação para a Investigação e Desenvolvimento de Ciências
FECYT	Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology
DoA	Description of Action
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IBERCIVIS	Fundación Ibercivis
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
SfC	Science for Change
UNIPD	Università degli Studi di Padova
WP	Work Package

Table 1: Acronyms used in deliverable D7.1 on Data Management Plan

2. Introduction

This document contains the **NEWSERA Project Data Management Plan (DMP)**. The **tools and strategies used for providing open access** to research data are also presented.

The structure of this document responds to the **Open Research Data Pilot of the European Commission**, which seeks to enable open access and reuse of research data generated by Horizon 2020 projects. There are **two main pillars** to the Pilot: developing a Data Management Plan (DMP) and providing open access to research data, if possible.

The first part of this deliverable (sections: 2-7) specifically includes **all the issues regarding the DMP**. After briefly introducing the objectives and methodologies of the NEWSERA project and ethics as a cross-cutting issue embedding all the project, all the details on the generated data and the implementation of FAIR principles are explained.

The second part (sections: 8-10) corresponds to the **second pillar of the Open Research Data Pilot of the European Commission about open access**. The sections addressed in the corresponding sections deals with some topics already covered in the DMP, but putting emphasis in crucial aspects of the FAIR approach: allocations of resources, data security, as well as other ethical topics including details of incidental findings, management of risks or disturbances, along with some final ethical considerations.

Some modifications have been introduced in this final version, related to the next aspects:

- It is noted that Science for Change, the lead partner, will take over the management of the data that were generated during the development of NEWSERA, replacing IBERCIVIS as of DATE.
- Explanation is provided on the modifications of the informed consent forms - including explicitly the name of the Data Protection Officer - and the clarification on "vulnerable persons" - children, young minors, and vulnerable adults -, modifications that were requested by the Commission after the review of the first period of the project.
- It is explained that a public acknowledgement of NEWSERA pilots and their representatives was introduced on the website, according to their informed consent.
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- Five new references have been added: four of them associated with three NEWSERA documents and another one to the Kampal

3. The NEWSERA project

The overall objective of NEWSERA was to show the possibilities of **citizen science as an inclusive, broad and powerful channel of scientific communication**. Citizen science allows for increased trust in scientific communication and, in turn, in science in general. While opening up science and innovation to the whole society, citizen science improves scientific training and promotes critical thinking, reducing the possibilities of false news.

Our challenge focused on promoting citizen science as a tool for scientific communication, defining specific strategies together with the **quadruple helix stakeholders** -that is, **communities** including the third sector, **the State** and public sector, **the market** and private sector, and **academia** - **as well as science and data journalists**.

3.1 Objectives

The specific objectives were the following:

1. Evaluate the current effectiveness of science communication and the perception of stakeholders participating in citizen science projects.
2. Create five Science Communication Labs -the #CitSciComm Labs- addressed to quadruple helix stakeholders and science and data journalists, in order to advance the state-of-the-art of science communication.
3. Interlink data journalism principles and citizen science and find new ways to explore common goals and collaborative efforts between citizen scientists and data journalists.
4. Develop improved ways to measure and assess science communication.
5. Identify good practices to ensure quality, reliability and increased trust in science communication and science.
6. Produce five innovation blueprints, addressed to quadruple helix stakeholders and science and data journalists, to guarantee project replicability.
7. Provide policy guidelines to increase trust in science communication.
8. Provide new contents and methodologies for formal and informal teaching in science communication within scientific disciplines.
9. Suggest new incentive mechanisms to involve academic scientists in science communication.
10. Use advanced data mining techniques to provide a framework to evaluate the effectiveness of the different science communication strategies; the impact and efficiency of such strategies will be validated through the definition of KPIs.

11. Communicate and disseminate the project actions to replicate NEWSERA and beyond.
12. Embed and put into practice a highly inclusive engagement model, based on mutual learnings.
13. Embed the ethics dimension in relation to the participation of citizens in research, data protection aspects, and in relation to the perception of science and science communication of quadruple helix stakeholders. findings and science communication strategies in citizen science projects.

3.2 Methodology

NEWSERA deeply analysed and evaluated the strategies addressed to quadruple helix stakeholders in citizen science projects as the new paradigm for science communication. NEWSERA used a bottom-up approach to co-design strategies for selected Citizen Science projects, in order to improve their science communication practices and their impact towards each **quadruple helix stakeholder group**. These strategies were developed with the involvement of **science and data journalists and science communicators**, to propose innovative ways to open up science and innovation to the whole society, and increase trust in science communication.

Methodologies used in NEWSERA implied generation and management of data in diverse ways. That information was generated through the first survey on ‘Science Communication through Citizen Science’, the #CitSciCom Labs and the results obtained from the Kampal tool. The management of the corresponding data was handled as planned and **without incident**.

3.2.1 The survey on ‘Science Communication through Citizen Science’

The survey on ‘NEWSERA - Portrait of Citizen Science Communication Strategies in EU Citizen Science Projects’ (with the corresponding **form** being available at Giardullo, P., Citarella, M.A., & Neresini, F. (2021) as well as the **scientific publication** by Giardullo et al. (2023)) was addressed to responsables for citizen science projects based in the EU and UK, including some general information about the project and about the ways used to communicate and engage with its communities and other stakeholders.

The aim of the survey was to paint a clearer picture of the science communication strategies carried out by citizen science projects and to get in touch with projects to include in the co-creation Labs that would be organised as part of NEWSERA. **Complete details** on ethical issues and data management about the survey were **included in deliverable D8.3 H-POPD Requirement No 3**.

3.2.2 The #CitSciComm Labs

The **NEWSERA #CitSciComm Labs aimed at co-designing innovative strategies** helping to improve the quality and the effectiveness of science communication, and the perception of and trust in science.

In the co-design process, both **digital communication strategies and non-digital participatory strategies** were considered and targeted for the specific audiences.

The main **objectives** of #CitSciComm Labs, all of them achieved, were as follows:

- Creating a dialogue with all the stakeholders to improve engagement, effectiveness and trust in science communication and citizen science.
- Defining and assessing the concepts of Citizen Science Communication and Citizen Science Journalism in each of the labs.
- Using citizen science as an innovative tool to open up science and innovation to the quadruple-helix stakeholders.
- Developing formal and informal training for citizen and career scientists in science communication.
- Analysing the current reward mechanisms for scientists to get involved in science communication outside academia and co-create alternatives for recognition.
- Evaluating citizen science as a tool to fight misinformation in the post-factual era.

During the various meetings, **recordings and some photographs were taken, always with the informed consent of the participants.** This material corresponds to: the #CitSciComm Labs of the first two rounds held via zoom, the diverse follow-up meetings with the pilots also via zoom, the event on Data4CitSciNews held in Barcelona on 28 November 2022, the last round of #CitSciComm Labs face-to-face held in the three countries in Autumn 2022, and the final NEWSERA event held in Brussels on 29 March 2023. Corresponding details on the procedures of informed consent were included and updated in deliverable **D8.3 H-POPD Requirement No 3.**

All the published information about the Labs was being updated on the website throughout NEWSERA's development (<https://newsera2020.eu/labs/>).

3.2.3 Research based on the Kampal tool

As reflected in the Description of the action (DoA) part B, NEWSERA used the **Kampal tool for data analysis and visualisation.** The tool was used to analyse and represent multiple factors at the same time, such as the impact of a publication, or of a video, or the links on Twitter between actors in the same or different areas, either thematic or related to the quadruple helix groups, among other aspects. Several indicators have been used to quantify, in a simple way, the effectiveness of a communication campaign in a citizen science project, as shown e.g. in Figure 1, in which the interaction of citizens and researchers in Twitter for a citizen science

project for FECYT (2016-2017) is shown.

Figure 1: Citizen Science study for FECYT (2016-2017). The graph represents the interactions of citizens and researchers on Twitter. Each node is a user, the links between nodes are the mentions or retweets between them. In this case, several communities were identified with their respective leaders, number of members and productivity indicators.

The tool had previously been used by the NEWSERA partner IBERCIVIS together with members of the spin-off of the University of Zaragoza also named Kampal, to analyse, among many other cases, the global reach of citizen science in academia. It also offers advantages over other similar tools, as it incorporates digital social media.

Kampal allows the **extraction of data from existing open data repositories and platforms**, according to their **corresponding policies** as well as **technological constraints**, all of them rapidly evolving (<https://developer.twitter.com/en/developer-terms/agreement-and-policy>).

Examples indicated in the NEWSERA GA were: research project websites, repositories where citizen science information is stored and where citizens collaborate with researchers, research networks where researchers publish their publications (Google scholar), research or innovation repositories where volunteers and companies participate (GitHub), social networks as the main multidirectional channel of communication between all actors (Twitter), or open access services to public data of the European Commission. Importantly, **the NEWSERA pilot projects expressed their preferences** through the initial Kampal survey, so for each of them

different sources were monitored according to **their most used communication channels**. The four sources finally analysed were: **Google Scholar, Google Alerts, Twitter and YouTube**.

The main usefulness of the tool is that it allows project managers **to know, in real-time, the impacts of their communication actions, part of their strategy co-designed with NEWSERA**, through different functionalities and in a visual way that makes it easier to understand those impacts, in particular according to the different 4H-stakeholders and data journalists.

Finally, Kampal with its associated tools provided **Key Performance Indicators** on the impact of the communication strategies designed and implemented in WP3 and WP4, and evaluated in WP5. As an example of the results that Kampal's tools provided, we briefly mention here the concept of clustering applied on Twitter. With this technique, **different communities related to the pilots were identified**: their size, how many of the elements of a network collaborate with each other, who is the leader, or associated sub-communities. This helped to check, for example, whether each citizen science community interacts with the sub-communities of the quadruple helix (academic scientists, industry, policy makers, civil society). We can mention **some real cases**, such as the knowledge of the relevance of a certain node in a community of Twitter users, or the discovery of a relevant but unknown user for the project, aspects that have allowed a **dynamic design of communication strategies** in order **to improve the desired impact**.

Regarding Data Management, all data that Kampal obtained from sources such as Google, YouTube or Twitter were treated according to the current European regulations contained in the GDPR, [Regulation \(EU\) 2016/679](#). The previous experience of IBERCIVIS in this type of research together with the Institute for Biocomputation and Physics of Complex Systems (BIFI) of the University of Zaragoza (Álvarez et al, 2015, Pelacho et al. 2021a) was essential for the elaboration of reports as well as as assessment. The analyses of the data collected by Kampal from the four sources mentioned above were used to produce customised reports for the projects that so wished. The final reports of the pilots, carried out by IBERCIVIS and Kampal, will also be published in Zenodo if they want to do so and give their explicit informed consent. The corresponding databases with personal data will be destroyed after the agreed period once the project has finished. The analyses carried out by Kampal were also applied to the development of NEWSERA; in this case, the resulting final document by Pelacho et al. (2023) has been published on Zenodo in open access, in accordance with the FAIR principle which has been followed at all times to the greatest extent possible.

Finally, **in the second half of March of 2023**, there was a **shift in Twitter policy** that affected Kampal's ability to use Twitter information. Kampal Social was using the Twitter API v1.1 to track and monitor keywords and users on that social network. On March 14, 2023, Twitter discontinued this API service <https://developer.twitter.com/en/updates/changelog> and only version 2.0 of the API remains operative. To use the new API, it is necessary to apply for a new application process that requires approval from Twitter, which can take several

weeks. If access is approved, the new limits <https://developer.twitter.com/en/docs/twitter-api/rate-limits> established by the platform further restrict access to the flow of information. In any case, monitoring of projects from other sources (news alerts, Google Scholar and YouTube) continued until the end of NEWSERA in March 2023, and for Twitter until 14 March 2023.

4. Ethics at the NEWSERA project

4.1 Social justification of working with human beings

As we stated in preliminary documents as well as in the NEWSERA GA, while science communication and citizen science can play a role in participatory democracy and active citizenship, decisions may involve **important ethical questions** for the **advancement of science**, for **meeting societal challenges**, and for the **development of new policies**.

In consequence, aspects such as data quality and integrity, data sharing and intellectual property, conflicts of interest, and potential exploitation of participants in citizen science projects (Resnick et al. 2015), were evaluated from the very beginning. Following the participatory governance approach - a characteristic of citizen science - the establishment of agreements and guidelines for ethical conduct must also be a co-created process whenever possible. In this sense, deliverable **D7.2. Identifying ethical aspects as a cross-cutting issue in NEWSERA actions**, by Pelacho (2021b) and published at M20, refers to the multiple ethical aspects, on the one hand co-identified in the practice of citizen science, and on the other hand, during the development of NEWSERA, following the participatory governance approach through co-creation processes.

Given the ethical requirements within communication following citizen science projects, a co-creation process was developed with NEWSERA participants - defining proper criteria in a bottom-up process. In addition to issues related to data protection and the recruitment of participants, these ethics requirements were developed. Both the procedure and the results served to elaborate the adaptable guide for each citizen science project, with the necessary changes. (Magalhaes et al. 2023)

Since the inception of NEWSERA, we were aware that **ethical aspects are at the core of citizen science, science communication and dissemination**, and therefore, they consist of a **cross-cutting issue in the NEWSERA project**. We understand citizen science and science as a service for addressing current societal challenges, including its communication and dissemination. Therefore, we wanted this deliverable to be a **living document, which was able to adapt to new social and community needs**, also during the development of our own project.

Now, at the very end of the project, we are reflecting here the relevant issues that have been addressed, and also **documented and published**, in this respect.

4.2 Executive summary of deliverables related to D7.1

As we have indicated, D7.1, together with D7.2, D8.1, D8.2 and D8.3, include the main aspects of data management and ethical requirements of the NEWSERA project.

- **D7.2. Report on ethical aspects as a cross-cutting issue in NEWSERA actions.** The deliverable, by Pelacho (2021b), was published by M20 and is available on Zenodo repository. It consists of a report on the ethical aspects co-identified with citizen science participants, following the participatory governance approach through a co-creation process, and including inclusiveness aspects.
- **D8.1. H-Requirement No. 1** focuses on the **procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit research participants** that must be applied. Copies of opinions/approvals by ethics committees and/or competent authorities for the research with humans will be obtained and kept on file. The final version of this document was updated in June 2023.
- **D8.2. POPD-Requirement No. 2** implies that the **contact details of the Data Protection Officer (DPO)** had and have to be available to all data subjects involved in the research. This document was delivered by July 2020. After the review by the Commission we were requested to explicitly include the name of Francisco Sanz (IBERCIVIS) as DPO (all contact details were already included but not the name of the DPO). We did so in all the templates for informed consent, registration or evaluation forms, and where necessary. The **corrected version** of this document was delivered **by July 2021 and updated by June 2023**.
- **D8.3. H-POPD-Requirement No. 3** deals with the **informed consent procedures** implemented for the participation of humans. NEWSERA developed the necessary **informed consent/assent forms and information sheets** (in language and terms intelligible to the participants). **Children** could be involved in activities, due to the close connection between citizen science and STEM education. Also other vulnerable persons, in terms of data protection, could participate. Details on how they had to assent as well as the consent of legal representatives are explained in this deliverable. Also in this deliverable a correction was requested by the Commission: we needed to explicitly affirm that **children, young minors, and vulnerable adults** are the vulnerable persons we refer to in the deliverable, as well to present the necessary templates for them. The **corrected version** of this document was delivered **by July 2021 and updated by 2023**.

5. Data management at the NEWSERA project

5.1 Data quality and integrity

The **'Ambition'** relevant section within the Description of the action (DoA) part B refers to the idea of **'NEWSERA: Beyond the state-of-the-art in Science Communication'**. One of the issues deals with the topic 'Addressing ethical and governance issues in science communication and citizen science'. We highlight here **the most relevant information regarding data quality and integrity, under the NEWSERA approach.**

In order to make **citizen science** increasingly **reliable** (as to its understanding as true science) and **legitimate** (as to its use in policy making), citizens should acquire knowledge about the conditions to make **citizen science highly relevant and performed by applying the necessary ethical standards.** For us, it has been very important to notice that by saying 'citizens' we here refer to professional scientists, politicians, representatives of companies and industry, along with the rest of society including citizen scientists, as in the end, we are all citizens.

At completion of the project and based on the feedback from the participants, we can state that NEWSERA has reinforced the idea that ethical aspects range from raising awareness about **science integrity, accuracy, reliability, precision, objectivity, sustainability,** and other elements of research ethics, to values involved in performing research with human subjects and data. We have shared the ideas on while recognizing the important benefits that citizen science offers to science and the whole society, some experts on ethical aspects of science (Resnik et al, 2015) have pointed out that "citizen science also raises ethical issues that should be addressed before projects begin and throughout the course of scientific investigation". In particular, they highlight **aspects related to data quality and integrity, data sharing and intellectual property, conflicts of interest, and potential exploitation of participants.** So, they explain that "**to promote ethical research, scientists should develop guidelines** for involvement of citizens in research, communicate effectively with participants at the outset of their involvement in research projects, carefully oversee their work, develop appropriate publication practices, take steps to address conflicts of interest, and provide lay volunteers with education and training on the responsible conduct of research" (Resnik et al, 2015).

Although we agreed this proposal is necessary, **NEWSERA took a step further,** also adopting the **complementary bottom-up approach:** the definition and establishment of ethical guidelines is not an issue that should be dealt with exclusively by one of the parties. On the contrary, according to the **participatory governance approach** the establishment of agreements and guidelines for ethical conduct must also be a **co-created process whenever possible,** in which it is not taken for granted that professional scientists are always the best able to lead the process. In any case, the presence of people with expertise - and experiential - knowledge in ethics is undoubtedly required. Alignment as (and where) appropriate

in the collaborative relationship between citizens and scientists was at the basis of this objective, in order to co-create good practices, skills, and trust. **Existing norms and practices both in creating good science and ethical research were discussed and shared**, particularly during the **specific workshops on ethics in science communication, including misinformation issues (Round 2 of NEWSERA #CitSciComm Labs)**. The goals were both to improve citizen science and citizens (professional scientists or not) **awareness** about it, and to make the exchanges and interactions between society as a whole and professional scientists. These collaborations allowed, on the one hand, nonprofessional scientists to acquire - or improve - all relevant scientific knowledge and skills, and on the other hand, everyone to acquire - or improve - their **ethical training** in order to further organise and perform research by confidently establishing relationships among all the parties. Some of the results were collected in the **'Guide of science communication in citizen science projects and citizen science journalism'** (Magalhães et al. 2023).

5.2 Protection of personal data

In accordance with NEWSERA Description of the action (DoA), adequate measures to ensure personal data protection and confidentiality were taken, according to [Regulation \(EU\) 2016/679](#) on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and the national implementations on personal data protection law when approved.

General procedures included in the research protocol to safeguard the privacy of study subjects were indicated as follows:

- Written informed consents will be obtained from all participants in the study to use their personal data.
- All materials obtained in the framework of the project (questionnaires, sensors) will be identified through a code - the name and/or other personal data that could allow the identification of the participant will never be indicated. This unique identifier will link all basic data required for the study. The master key file linking the centre's study numbers with personal identifiers will be maintained in a password protected file with limited access.
- All files containing personal data will be stored in encrypted and password-locked files. Access to these files will be limited to authorised project personnel.
- Only researchers linked to the project will have access to personal data. Participants will know from informed consents who have access to the data, the name of the responsible and the personnel in relation to their positions.
- Reported study results will pertain to analysis of aggregate data. No individual's name will be associated with any published or unpublished report of this study.

- All project personnel will be trained in the importance of confidentiality of individual records and required to sign a confidentiality agreement.

In all EU countries, in NEWSERA development specifically, **the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) - Regulation (EU) 2016/679** on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data **has been applied**.

More details in this respect were and are provided in next sections and in deliverables corresponding to WP8 on Ethics requirements.

5.3 Main guidelines to elaborate the DMP

In order to create this DMP we mainly followed the next references (see section 12):

- [Regulation \(EU\) 2016/679](#) on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, (GDPR)
- The guidelines provided by the European Commission on [FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020](#)
- The [guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020 v3.2](#)
- The JRC Technical Report [Survey report: data management in Citizen Science Projects](#) (Schade et al, 2016)
- The [Report from CSA 2017 and Future Outlook](#), by Citizen Science Association Data & Metadata Working Group (Bowser et al, 2017)
- The [Geneva Declaration on Citizen Science Data and Metadata standards](#) (Ceccaroni et al, 2018)
- The [ECSA principles for citizen science](#)

6. Data summary at NEWSERA

The data set foreseen to be generated during the project is shown below; the partner responsible for managing it was also indicated as well as the WPs related to their generation. IBERCIVIS has been the partner responsible for all the Data management, albeit some concrete datasets were also managed together with other partners, as it is indicated in the next subsection. From the 31/03/2023, official end date of the project, SfC - partner leading NEWSERA - will be in charge of the data management, and Rosa Arias the main responsible. More details on the work of the Data Protection Officer (DPO) are provided in deliverable D8.2. POPD-Requirement No. 2.

6.1 Type of data

The types of data collected, generated, analysed and managed in the NEWSERA project as well as the origin of the data, both personal and non-personal, are detailed in section 3 of this document. Their treatment is extensively explained in the WP8 deliverables.

The objectives and methodologies of NEWSERA absolutely exclude both the collection of biological samples and sensitive information on humans, which would require special treatment.

6.2 Databases generated within the NEWSERA project

nº	Dataset name	Institution in charge	Related WPs
1	List of consortium partners and EAB members	SfC/IBERCIVIS	1, 7, 8
2	List of projects to contact with	IBERCIVIS	1, 6, 7, 8
3	Data generated through the survey	UNIPD/IBERCIVIS	2, 7, 8
4	List of participants in activities	IBERCIVIS	1, 3, 7, 8
5	Data generated through #CitSciComm Labs	IBERCIVIS	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8
6	Newsletter subscribers	FB/IBERCIVIS	6, 7, 8
7	Data generated by navigating on web	FB/IBERCIVIS	6, 7, 8
8	Data generated by Kampal tool	IBERCIVIS	3, 4, 5, 7, 8

Table 1. Databases generated, responsible partners and WPs involved

As we can see, datasets 3, 5 and 8 are related to research data.

The corresponding eight WP were devoted to:

WP1 - Coordination and project management

WP2 - Analysis of Citizen Science as a Science Communication Tool

WP3 - Co-design of innovative strategies in Citizen Science Communication

WP4 - The NEWSERA Pilots: Implementing the concepts of Citizen Science Communication and Citizen Science Journalism

WP5 - Evaluation and impact assessment: the legacy of NEWSERA

WP6 - Dissemination and Communication Actions

WP7 - Ethics and Data Protection strategies in NEWSERA

WP8 - Ethics requirements

The databases created were as foreseen, with the exception of the one corresponding to the Newsletter because this was not carried out. The management of the databases is described in sections 7.4 and 7.5.

7. FAIR Data

This specific subsection was devoted to each one of the FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable - Data properties, putting an special emphasis on open access to data research, as the Open Research Data Pilot of the European Commission recommends.

In this section, the working scheme of the DMP published by [EU.Citizen-Science](#) was followed, in which IBERCIVIS remains working. The necessary modifications and adaptations to the aspects and peculiarities of NEWSERA were made.

7.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

The concept of findability refers to the viability of the information to be located by other users. To achieve this goal the necessary metadata were provided to help in the identification of the different datasets generated during the project. In this sense, only a dataset - the one corresponding to the NEWSERA - Portrait of Citizen Science Communication Strategies in EU Citizen Science Projects (Giardullo, P., Citarella, M.A., & Neresini, F. 2021) - resulted as an output to be shared.

As provided by the open document The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship (Wilkinson et al. 2016) we planned, where possible:

- assign a globally unique and persistent identifier to (meta)data
- describe data which rich metadata
- include clearly and explicitly in the metadata the identifier of the data it describes
- register on index (meta)data in a searchable resource

This data is stored at Zenodo and linked to the NEWSERA web page, therefore downloadable openly. The corresponding database to the initial Newsera survey, which was answered completely anonymously and was the basis for the openly published results by [Giardullo et al. 2023](#) and is available under demand. In addition, the survey form is already available at Zenodo (Giardullo, P., Citarella, M.A., & Neresini, F. 2021). The anonymous data and metadata will be uploaded to Zenodo within three months of the end of the project, providing a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) that allows editing/updating these files once published if necessary. We point out that at the end of the form survey there was an additional question for those who wanted to explicitly express their interest in participating in NEWSERA as pilots; this part, as indicated, was only intended to contact these people. The corresponding database - containing the project name and personal contact data - is treated in exactly the same way as the other personal data sets (section 7.2.1).

We will search for other datasets which can be used for the purposes of the project. As it is indicated in the Description of the action (DoA), NEWSERA will work in close collaboration with the seven projects funded in the topic Swafs-19

in order to **create synergies, join efforts and avoid duplication**: [RETHINK](#), [CONCISE](#), [QUEST](#), [ParCos](#), [GlobalScape](#), [ENJOI](#) and [TRESKA](#). Like these projects, NEWSERA is complying with the dissemination obligations and making active efforts to freely share, in a timely manner and as appropriate, the research strategies, methodologies, and raw and analysed data deriving from our activities, including evaluation, with the other projects funded under the SwafS call. Through mutual learning exercises and with a special interest to avoid duplication of efforts and expand knowledge on the science communication field we will share the information collected and non-personal data that support the synergies between these projects, according to FAIR principles. In addition, NEWSERA will join efforts with [EU-Citizen.Science](#), the CSA mapping the landscape of citizen science in Europe, to enrich their activities in communication in citizen science, or the mutual-learning platform. This will allow the selection of ongoing H2020 CS projects under which to execute the NEWSERA pilots and Science Communication Labs, such as, for example, [D-NOSES](#), [CitieS-Health](#) or [ACTION](#). Moreover, we open the possibility to collaborate with projects funded under Horizon Europe that can guarantee the legacy and sustainability of NEWSERA, such as [IMPETUS](#), [COALESCE](#) or others.

All this data will be useful for quadruple-helix stakeholders - communities, Public Authorities, Business, and academia - related to citizen science, as well as science and data journalists.

7.2 Making data openly accessible

7.2.1 Which data have been made available to the public

Next paragraphs correspond to the previous version of this document.

All data will be made available except those containing personal data and personally identifiable information. Personal data will not be openly accessible, nor available to third parties to protect participants' privacy.

The personal data processed in the project is not made publicly accessible, but kept closed and unavailable to third parties, in particular:

- the **identity of participants** - including audios, videos and images - in personal interviews and in group activities such as #CitSciComm Labs (online or offline), unless they explicitly indicate that they can be made public, through written informed consent (provided in deliverable 8.2).
- **personal email addresses** voluntarily provided through the survey in order to participate in the project activities.

Data resulting from individual forms - for surveys, interviews and group activities - used for research publications will be **anonymized prior to online storage**.

Transcriptions and questionnaires, as well as the photographs and recordings of those who do not give their explicit consent to publication, are stored in secure

space by SfC instead of Ibercivis in the terms agreed, after the end of the project, on the 31st March 2023..

In this last version of the DMP we add two points regarding the previous statements:

- As for the #CitSciComm Labs (online in the first and second round, face-to-face in the third round, as well as the Data4CitSciNews event and NEWSERA final event) only one participant did not give their consent for photographs publication and this was strictly applied.
- As for the identity of participants representing the pilots, NEWSERA team posed the convenience of giving them proper recognition, in sight of their high level of implication and co-created actions. Pilots' representatives gave their corresponding informed consents, so they were included on the NEWSERA website: <https://newsera2020.eu/labs/list-of-participants/>.

7.2.2 How the data will be made available

During the development of the project, various data and partial results (e.g. statistics of visitors to #CitSiComm Labs and documents on its development) will be made available to interested parties, through one of the following means:

- Newsletters, reports and/or other publications on the NEWSERA website
- Local partner's websites
- Partner's social media
- Collaborative platforms (Zoom, Padlet, Mural or similar)
- Zenodo repository

The detailed data were available to all partners of the consortium through the shared project unit (with the exception of personal data stored in the premises of each partner, as indicated in the previous section). Access to this unit was restricted to project partners. If co-researchers participating had wished to access for research purposes during the project, these had to be openly shared upon request. So far this has not been the case. From the end of the project on, the data to be stored will be kept in the Zenodo data repository.

7.2.3 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data

Data has been published in standard file formats on Zenodo repository, therefore they will also be accessible using standard tools (as the indicated ones in the previous section).

7.2.4 Where data, metadata, and documentation are deposited

Personal data will be stored on a local secured server by the partner responsible depending where the data comes from in each case. Responsible partners are indicated in *Table 1. Databases generated, responsible partners and WPs involved, within subsection 6.2.*

Data and associated metadata to be public are stored on a central drive, on the project platform and on Zenodo.

7.2.5 How access will be provided in case there are any restrictions

No restrictions are foreseen; if required, the appropriate open software will be provided to access the data or export it to standard formats.

7.3 Making data interoperable

In order to achieve interoperability among data, every dataset generated within NEWSERA will have the necessary metadata.

For all types of data we use standard vocabularies according to PPSR_CORE in case of citizen science projects and other ontologies such as provided by schema.org for other kinds of data which was developed for research on and with citizen science.

In the very unlikely case of using uncommon vocabulary or to generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, we will provide mapping of them.

7.4 Increase data re-use

In order to achieve the widest re-use possible, **diverse Creative Commons Licences have been used** for all data to be preserved, depending on the different data types.

The data collected and analysed during the project were made **openly available alongside the project** in the way indicated in next section 8 on 'allocation of resources'. That is, deliverables and publications have been uploaded at Zenodo no later than 3 months after release or whenever we had the OK from the reviewers, whereas datasets will be uploaded at the end of the project, within 3 months by the closing of project activities (M39). As for patents, NEWSERA has not got this type of product.

For all **shared information re-usability by third parties is guaranteed**. No Personal Identifiable Information has been/will be shared with third parties.

A **quality assurance process** was developed from the beginning of the project, through the work of partners and Project Coordinator, who are experts on diverse matters.

As for the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable, SfC **guarantees 10 years from the end of the project (31st March 2023)**.

As stated at the introduction, according to Open Access H2020 Pilot, NEWSERA's aims have gone **further to the FAIR principles**. Therefore, from the very beginning the DMP also addressed next points: allocations of resources, data security, ethical aspects and other considerations.

8. Allocations of resources

Alongside NEWSERA development **IBERCIVIS servers** were used by the Consortium to store the data in SQL and noSQL databases in a FAIR way. From the end of NEWSERA onwards, **Science for Change** will be in charge of the storage, protection, and management of the data. According to GDPR, the data managed, protected and stored so far by IBERCIVIS (and UNIPD and Formicablu as indicated in Table 1), are and will be fully transferred to SfC. The GDPR requirements are strictly accomplished as no data is transferred to third parties.

The handling of the local servers and Zenodo repository as well as all data management issues related to the project failed in the responsibility of the DPO, Mr. Francisco Sanz from Ibercivis.

Data and/or deliverables were uploaded at Zenodo by the coordinator with the support of FB, responsible leader of WP6 on dissemination and communication actions. Public deliverables at Zenodo were linked to the NEWSERA website.

Deliverables and publications were uploaded no later than 3 months after release or whenever we had the OK from the reviewers.

Regarding costs:

- The data is guaranteed for **10 years on unfunded effort by Science for Change**.
- Archiving at **Zenodo is free of charge**, so there are no additional costs for its usage.
- Deliverables will be published under a **Creative Commons licence**, therefore **free of charge**.

The responsible partner for Data Management is Ibercivis. The contact details were provided to all the participants in each one of the activities, as it is indicated in deliverable **D8.2 POPD Requirement No.2**.

9. Data security

With respect to data recovery, personal or non-personal, **IBERCIVIS is the partner responsible for data management:** complete contact details as well as all rights of participants regarding their data were provided in each one of the project activities.

The main features, as it is indicated in the Description of Action (DoA) -part B, were indicated as follows:

- No data of a citizen will be collected without his/her permission
- Information will be only used for the purposes covered by agreement, and will not be retained except as required for these purposes
- Information will not be made public or provided to third parties without explicit permission
- Contractual and technical controls will be applied to prevent information becoming inadvertently available to third parties

As far as the secure storage and transfer of sensitive data is concerned, it must be stressed that, as planned, **no sensitive data were collected during the NEWSERA project.** The project is focused on citizen science as a tool for better science communication, so the topics addressed were not related to any sensitive data (as, for example, health, religion, or political ideas of participants).

Children and young minors could have been involved in activities, due the close connection between citizen science and STEM/STEAM education, involving Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics, along with Arts and creativity. Details on how they assent as well as the consent of legal representatives were provided in deliverable **D8.3 H-POPD-Requirement No.3.** NEWSERA similarly had to proceed in case of **vulnerable adults.** The double objective was to **promote maximum inclusiveness, together with maximum protection of privacy of each singular person.**

In fact, **no vulnerable people (children, young minors or vulnerable adults) eventually participated in NEWSERA activities.** The start of NEWSERA was simultaneous with the start of the health crisis (in Europe). As explained in different deliverables - particularly those related to events (WP6) - the development of the activities was mostly online, with the necessary adaptations that made open participation impossible. When from November 2022 onwards, face-to-face meetings could be held (third round of CitSciComm Labs on 3 November, Data4CitSciNews event on 28 November, and the final event on 29 March 2023), health conditions were not adequate to the promotion of participants who might be vulnerable in any way.

In any case and as above mentioned, following the indications of the Commission Officer after the review of NEWSERA Period 1, we modified two aspects of deliverables D8.2 Report on POPD Requirement No. 2 and D8.3 Report on H-POPD

Requirement No. 3. On the one hand, we introduced the name of Francisco Sanz, as DPO, in all the informed consent templates (and not only his contact details as we had done). On the other hand, we made it explicit, in all the corresponding statements, that when we spoke of vulnerable persons we were referring to: children, young minors and vulnerable adults. This version of the DMP includes the corresponding new informed consent template, as well as another example of the introduction of the DPO name and surname in one of the anonymous forms for the Labs evaluation (ANNEX I).

As indicated in the previous version, the **Protection of Personal Data has been and will be guaranteed** through the actions explained in deliverables included in WP8. Specifically **D8.2 Report on POPD Requirement No. 2** and **D8.3 Report on H-POPD Requirement No. 3**, including data sharing, data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction of personal data, as well as templates of the informed consent forms and information sheets (in language and terms intelligible to the participants).

10. Other ethical aspects

All the ethical requirements in relation to data management were covered by the closely related deliverables D8.1, D8.2, D8.3 and D7.2 together with this document D7.1 on DMP.

10.1 Details of incidental findings

Foreseeing possible contingencies of all kinds, these documents were periodically reviewed by the coordinating partner of the project in collaboration with the leaders of the different WPs as well as with the members of the Executive Advisory Board.

For the purposes of this project, 'incidental findings' were understood as findings about illegal/unethical acts by individuals or groups, as well as information from workshops that might concern third-parties. That is the reason for, on the one hand, we guarantee our ethical-legal behaviour in all activities. On the other side, we asked for participants - co-researchers - their informed consent including their compromise of not providing false information.

As explained, these documents were posed as living documents and have been reviewed according to the cross-cutting nature of the ethical aspects, during the development of the whole project and especially in view of the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic and the necessity of methodological adaptations.

10.2 Management of risks or disturbances

Regarding risks, we can affirm that they are minimal at NEWSERA. That is, the possible risk is one that does not exceed in probability or magnitude the one that could be expected in the daily work activity, including routine checks.

The only disturbance may be the use of participants' time, but they provided it voluntarily as co-researchers within the project. On the other hand, necessary travel or other expenses were covered by the project. In the case of journalists providing their professional services, they were properly paid.

Regarding NEWSERA activities, conducting surveys and interviews on topics that do not include any sensitive information did not involve more than the above mentioned minimal risks. Therefore, no prevention mechanisms were proposed in this regard.

As for protection of vulnerable groups - **children, young minors, vulnerable adults** - it has been explained in previous section on Data security and it is more detailed in deliverable **D8.3 H-POPD-Requirement No.3**, corrected by July 2021.

10.3 Other considerations

Finally, as it is stated in the JRC document Survey report on data management in Citizen Science Projects, we paid attention to “the variation in ethical and legal issues related to data gathering, sharing and storage depending on countries and cultures and promote best practices for addressing them.” (pag. 44). The consideration of the different cultures and backgrounds is a minimum requirement for achieving our objective of developing a co-created process, based on a bottom-up approach as much as possible.

11. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Key Performance Indicators (KPI) were defined to validate the impact and efficiency of decisions made. Next examples of KPIs related to the DMP were included in the first version of this document:

Personal

- Number of registered participants, that is, quantity of personal data
- Number of participants who request their personal data and download it
- Number of participants who request to withdraw from the project

Statistics

- Space (in GB) occupied by the databases
- Number of requests for access to anonymized project information

- Number of data repositories in Zenodo with DOI (Findable)
- Number of Open Access data repositories (Accessible)
- Number of times that the data is used in other projects (Interoperable + Reusable)

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ANNEX I

1-Informed consent form NEWSERA #CitSciComm Labs

Data and information treatment consent for participants in the NEWSERA #CitSciComm Labs

Dear NEWSERA collaborator,

Thank you very much for your participation in the NEWSERA #CitSciComm Lab, in (place/city) _____, on (date) _____.

We care about your data and your rights on them: all personal data are regulated under the GDPR, so you can exercise your rights according to this law.

We will not use personal data for the research. We will require personal data only to keep contact with you, if you agree to provide it to us. Personal Data will be stored until the end of the project and the correspondent final report.

We follow strict security procedures when storing personal data and under no circumstances we will transfer personal data to third parties. Ibercivis is responsible for processing and protecting all personal – and no personal – data obtained.

If you have any questions relating to this consent form or the way we are planning to use your information, please contact the NEWSERA's Data Protection Officer:

Francisco Sanz

Tel: +34 876 55 53 96

Email: ethics@ibercivis.es

Postal address: Ibercivis Foundation, Campus Río Ebro, Edificio I+D, C/ Mariano Esquillor, s/n, 50018 Zaragoza, Spain

To read more about data protection and how to exercise your rights on data, please read the full privacy notice on Protection Of Personal Data (POPD) attached or find it at this URL:

https://newsera2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/NEWSERA-Labs_Privacy-notice.pdf

Email address: _____

Having read the document below (POPD), please **tick the following boxes** if you agree.

- I have read the information presented in the POPD document (see the attached documentation or the link above).
- I know the possibility to ask any doubt regarding the project using face-to-face interview (offline or online) if possible, or by email at ethics@ibercivis.es.
- I consent to NEWSERA sending me information about the project by email.
- I know that I am doing voluntary contributions and I can leave the project when I want.
- I will not upload fake data with bad faith.
- I know that my personal data is regulated under the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
- I consent to the NEWSERA consortium using photographs and/or recordings including images of me, both internally and externally to promote the project. These images could be used in print and digital media formats, including print publications, websites, e-marketing, posters banners, advertising, film, social media, teaching and research purposes.
- I understand that images on websites can be viewed throughout the world and not just in Europe, and that some countries may not provide the same level of protection to the rights of individuals as European legislation provides.
- I understand that some images or recordings may be kept permanently once they are published and be kept as an archive beyond NEWSERA life.
- I agree to take part in this project.
- I agree to my name, surname and affiliation appearing in the corresponding public report.

Signed:

Name and surname:

Informed consent, related to images and/or recordings, given by the corresponding legal representatives of vulnerable persons (children, young minors, vulnerable adults) attending or present at the NEWSERA #CitSciComm Lab

- I consent to the NEWSERA consortium using photographs and/or recordings, including images of the vulnerable person I represent, as a parent or legal guardian. These images may be used both internally and externally to promote the project, in print and digital media formats, including print publications, websites, e-marketing, posters, advertising, film, social media, teaching and research purposes.
- I consent to the NEWSERA consortium using photographs and/or recordings, including images of the vulnerable person I represent, as a parent or legal guardian, **provided that in those images the child is not recognisable or identifiable in any way.** These images may be used both internally and externally to promote the project, in print and digital media formats, including print publications, websites, e-marketing, posters, advertising, film, social media, teaching and research purposes.
- I understand that images on websites can be viewed throughout the world and not just in Europe, and that some countries may not provide the same level of protection to the rights of individuals as European legislation provides.
- I understand that some images or recordings may be kept permanently once they are published and be kept as an archive beyond NEWSERA life.
- I legally represent the vulnerable person as a parent and I have the express or implied consent of the other parent to give this consent.

Signed:

Name and surname of parent or legal guardian:

Privacy notice on Protection Of Personal Data

PERSONAL DATA, PRIVACY AND PARTICIPANTS RIGHTS

We care about your data and your rights on them: all personal data are regulated under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) - Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, so you can exercise your rights according to this law.

What kind of data will we collect?

We will collect different types of data: one of them is mandatory and the rest are optional.

The mandatory fields are: first name, second name, country and email address. The optional data are the other demographic variables: gender, age, profile category and institution.

What will the information be used for?

We will use demographic data (gender, age, country, profile category and institution) only for statistical purposes. We will not use personal data for the research.

We will require personal - and optionally institutional - data to keep contact, if you agree to provide us with it.

Retention schedule

Personal Data will be stored until the end of the project and the publication of the correspondent final report: March 2023.

Who is responsible for data processing

Ibercivis is responsible for processing and protecting all personal - and no personal - data obtained. Ibercivis is a non-profit private foundation with NIF: G99330094. It was created on November 14, 2011 in Madrid. Its objectives are to continue with its work of collaboration with citizen research and carry out dissemination and training activities. It has a fiscal address in Campus Río Ebro, R&D Building, C/Mariano Esquillor, s/n, 50018 Zaragoza, Spain. The email address for ethical issues is ethics@ibercivis.es.

Personal data transfer

We follow strict security procedures when storing personal data. Under no circumstances we will transfer personal data to third parties outside the NEWSERA Consortium.

Rights and how to exercise them

You have the right to:

- Request information about whether we have personal data about you and, if so, what information we have, why we have it and how we are using it.
- Request access to your personal data. This allows you to receive a copy of your personal data and to correct any incomplete or incorrect information we have about you.
- Request personal data deletion. This allows you to delete or ask us to delete your personal data.
- Request to transfer your personal data to you or to a third party in an electronic and structured format - commonly known as the right to data portability.
- You can exercise any of these rights through the Newsera website or by email writing to ethics@ibercivis.es.
- You will not have to pay any fee to access your personal data - or to exercise any other of your rights.

2-Form for CitSciComm Labs evaluation explicitly including the Data Protection Officer name and surname

Evaluation of the #CitSciComm Lab workshop on Communication Ethics in Citizen Science - April 2022

This is a completely anonymous form addressed to all participants in NEWSERA's second set of #CitSciComm Labs. We believe that everyone's opinion is necessary for the success of the project and thus for the benefit of all.

We are not collecting any personal data through this form. We remind you that Ibercivis Foundation is responsible for processing and protecting all personal and no personal data obtained. Our Data Protection Officer is Francisco Sanz. You can contact him at ethics@ibercivis.es. To read more about data protection in NEWSERA and how to exercise your rights on data, here you have the pdf of the full privacy notice on Protection Of Personal Data (POPD): https://newsera2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/NEWSERA-Labs_Privacy-notice.pdf

The estimated response time is 3 - 5 minutes.
Thank you very much!